

The Relationship Between Business Model Innovation and Operational Performance of Incubator Enterprise

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Abstract

With the advent of service economy, business incubators have provided a series of service support by expanding the physical space and improving the infrastructure for newly established small and medium-sized high-tech enterprises, thereby reduced entrepreneurial risks and costs as well as increasing success rate of entrepreneurs, and promoted transformation of scientific and technological achievements. Business incubators have become an important carrier for cultivating enterprises and entrepreneurs, and supporting innovation and entrepreneurship. In the context of "Business startups and innovation", technological innovation changes rapidly. More and more attention has been paid to the function of business incubators. The mode of incubator industry has evolved from government-led to integrated participation of the government, universities and scientific research institutes. Finally, this dissertation verifies the positive impact of market orientation and business model innovation on the operation performance of the incubator, and the role of institutional environment as a regulatory variable in the middle. Incubator enterprises are the carrier of China's entrepreneurship, and also the basic support for scientific and technological progress and innovation. Moreover, they exist as a special type of business entity. This research provides a theoretical reference for the entrepreneurial operation of the incubator, and also improves the demonstration of the relationship between business model innovation and operation performance in special industries. At the same time, it provides a reference for policy-making, transformation and upgrading of China's incubator industry, and has an impetus significance to promote the incubation and the innovation of high-tech enterprises.

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Introduction

The development of China's technology business incubators has gradually changed from relying heavily on government support to market orientation enterprise management. It provides an important evidence base for the development direction and policy formulation of Chinese incubator enterprises in the future, and provides an important decision-making reference for improving incubator operational performance and enterprise management. At present, under the general trend of China's economic slowdown, it is an important issue worth discussing in order to diversify and promote the vitality of enterprises. According to the current development of China's incubator industry, independent enterprise management has become the mainstream. As a special market entity and an important carrier of innovation and entrepreneurship, incubators not only undertake the incubation work of small, medium and micro enterprises, but also form a market orientation mechanism. Faced with many challenges in the market competition as the main body of the enterprise, its operational performance is more complex than that of traditional enterprises, and it is necessary to consider the incubation efficiency, as well as economic and social efficiency, and market orientation and institutional environment also have correlative effect on it. Therefore, if an incubator company wants to play the function and effect of technology business incubation for a long time, and can operate independently in the market, it must first design a business model according to an enterprise's standards, and then formulate a correct development strategy. Analyzing the role of business model innovation in the operational performance of incubators from two themes of business model innovation - efficiency and novelty - deepens the research on business model innovation in incubators, and this study complements theories on business model innovation in the development of incubators in the Chinese context. This paper will mainly discuss the following issues: First, what is the relationship between market orientation and business model innovation? Second, what is the relationship between business model innovation and incubator operational performance? Third, does market orientation have a mediating effect on business model innovation and operational performance? Fourth, Does the institutional environment have a moderating effect on business model innovation and incubator operational performance? What is the relationship between business model innovation and operational performance? Fifth, what are the policy recommendations and practical implications of this study for incubator operation and management?

Literature review

Dependent variables: incubator operational performance

The research on the performance of technology business incubators at home and abroad has been in the process of dynamic development, and the relevant research results are constantly improving. Although the technology business incubator has the organizational structure of a general enterprise, it is a service-type intermediary organization and has certain public welfare attributes. Its goal is to help new ventures develop better. Therefore, different from the simple evaluation method of economic benefit and innovation benefit of ordinary enterprises, the evaluation of incubator performance also needs to incorporate social benefit and incubation benefit, etc., and the different emphasis also leads to the diversification of research perspectives. This paper sorts out the research results of domestic and foreign researchers, and summarizes the relevant conclusions as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Main research results related to incubator performance

Research Scholars	Main research results
Allen and Levine (1986)	Growth of incubatees, goals and philosophy of incubators, entry and exit policies, performance audit policies of incubatees, intellectual property protection policies, and services related to universities
Smilor (1987)	Growth and sustainability of incubation projects, incubator objectives and philosophy, shareholder rights protection policy, intellectual property protection policy, shared services
Mian (1997)	Growth and sustainability of incubated projects, survival rate and growth of incubated enterprises, contribution of university technology business incubators to the host university
Rice (1992)	Incubator structure and governance, financing and funding, target markets, shared services
Lindel and Hans (2002)	Financial dimension, financial dimension, human resource dimension, and supporting academic environment dimension
Lofsten and Lindelof (2005)	The characteristics of the incubatees themselves, human resource dimension, financial dimension, supporting academic environment dimension, and entrepreneurial outcome dimension
Liang (2004)	18 indicators are constructed to evaluate the incubation performance from three aspects: basic service conditions, comprehensive service functions, and incubation economic functions
Zhang (2006)	Five first-tier factors are proposed for the evaluation of incubator performance: incubator's own resources and operation and management, incubatees' development, entrepreneurial environment, social contribution, and technological innovation capability
Li (2008)	Establish an evaluation index system from three aspects: growth efficiency, incubation efficiency, and social efficiency
Yin et al. (2010)	Evaluate with two major indicators: incubated enterprises and social contribution
Liu (2012)	Analyze the impact of incubator networks on incubation performance in terms of innovation conversion, industrial upgrading, and business incubation
Xiao (2014)	Establish incubation performance evaluation system from five types of core services: preferential policy support, science and technology innovation services, property support services, investment and financing services and business support

Independent variable (IV1): Business model innovation

Business model innovation is a topic that has received attention from academia and society. After extensive research into definitions and conceptualizations, as well as numerous case studies, scholars in recent years have been calling for more general research, that is, empirical studies with large samples. Although scholars understand the importance of empirical

measurement for more specific and comprehensive research on business model innovation, measurement scales are still very scarce. Zott and Amit (2008) and Wei (2014) used a multi-item scale to distinguish and measure novelty-centered business model innovation and efficiency-centered business model innovation. Bock (2012) used a single indicator to measure business model innovation, that is, the proportion of enterprises committed to business model innovation. The author analyzed archived data from the 2006 IBM Global CEO Survey. The survey asked CEOs to allocate 100 points between three innovation types: product/service/market innovation, business model innovation and process, and operational innovation. Brea-Solís et al. (2015) used secondary data to measure business model innovation based on activity effects, technological change, and operational efficiency. Clauss Thomas and Kesting Tobias (2017) created a 3-level business model innovation scale to measure value creation innovation, value proposition innovation and value capture innovation. Searching for previous research results, therefore, in order to study the logical relationship between business model innovation and performance, it is necessary to clarify the structural system of business model innovation itself and the constituent elements indicators in various situations. Due to the low accuracy of other available scales, the scale developed by Zott and Amit (2007) is used in this paper. Constructing the scale of business model innovation and building a sound business model innovation mechanism can enrich the application of business model innovation at the theoretical level.

Mediating variable: market orientation

The concept of market orientation implies a reactive market orientation that satisfies the expressed needs of customers and also includes a proactive market orientation that satisfies the potential needs of customers. Narver, Slater and MacLachlan (2004) analyzed the impact of the proactive market orientation adopted by companies on the success rate of new products. The research results show that if companies want to innovate and ensure the success of new products, only reactive market orientation cannot meet the expectations of enterprises. In the process of new product success, the important role of proactive market orientation is obvious, and it is empirically supported in this study. In the research on the relationship between market orientation (reactive and proactive) and corporate performance, there are the following viewpoints: The relationship between market orientation (reactive and proactive) and corporate performance is complex, and It's not a straightforward linear relationship. Proactive market orientation and reactive market orientation are nonlinearly related to enterprise performance, and the two market orientations interact with enterprise performance. The study found that the existence of both market orientations is necessary, however, only when the two market orientations present a situation of one high and one low can the enterprise performance be improved (Atuahene-Gima & Slater, 2005). The interaction of reactive market orientation and innovative market orientation has an inverted U-shaped effect on enterprise performance (Chou & Yang, 2011). Tsai (2008) found that the characteristics of the external environment affect the correlation between the two market orientations and enterprise performance. Due to the adjustment of external environmental characteristics, the relationship between the two is curvilinear. Hierarchical regression analysis shows that under the condition of high degree of technological turbulence, reactive market orientation exceeding a certain level will cause damage to enterprise performance the relationship between proactive market orientation and enterprise performance exhibits an inverted U-shape under the condition of low degree of technological turbulence or competition intensity. The results also show that reactive and proactive market orientation are important determinants of enterprise performance. These findings deepen the understanding of the relationship between market orientation and enterprise performance. Tan and Liu (2014) suggested that the impact of reactive and proactive market orientation on performance is not

clear. In addition, some scholars pointed out that the relationship between the long-term and short-term performance of enterprises and the market orientation of the two types (proactive and reactive) is also affected by other factors, and the results are also diversified. The analysis results of Bodlaj et al. (2012) show that there are differences between the two complementary forms of proactive market orientation and reactive market orientation. Proactive market orientation is positively correlated with enterprise performance. Firms can improve innovation success and corporate performance by promoting market orientation proactiveness. Oswald et al. (2017) pointed out that research has made it clear that in the process of building successful and sustainable enterprises, reactive and proactive market orientation can bring certain benefits to improve corporate performance. Ozdemir's (2017) findings show that both reactive market orientation and proactive market orientation developed in different types of new product alliances can enable manufacturing firms to improve their new product performance and ultimately their overall performance. Another type of research is the impact of market orientation synergies on enterprise performance. Market orientation (reactive and proactive) both support positioning strategies (Iyer, 2018), and matching with differentiation and overall cost leadership strategies will have a positive impact on enterprise performance (Voola & O' Cass, 2010). The matching of reactive market orientation with market turbulence, technological turbulence and competition intensity has a positive correlation with enterprise performance, while the matching of proactive market orientation with market turbulence, technological turbulence and competition intensity has a negative correlation with enterprise performance (Wang et al., 2013). Some scholars have also aimed their research on issues related to market orientation and business model innovation. Combe Ian et al. (2012) discussed how market orientation promotes the strategic flexibility of business models based on open innovation, and the "ambidextrous" approach that combines market orientation and open innovation principles improves profitability. Rosanna Garcia (2018) found that when companies responded to the challenge of adopting a sustainable market orientation, they activated the availability and effectiveness of resources to stimulate business model innovation. Zheng and He (2019) draw on Narvei's scale to divide market orientation into two dimensions: proactive and responsive, and conduct research on efficient and novelty-centered business model innovations, and conclude that proactive and reactive market orientation is positively correlated with efficient and novelty-centered business model innovation. Zhou's (2019) research shows that market orientation (reactive and proactive) has a complex correlation with business model innovation. The above accumulated studies all use market orientation as an independent variable to study the correlation effect of market orientation. As an important activity of value information communication between enterprises and customers, market orientation often exists with some mediating effect. For example, some studies take market orientation as a mediating variable to study the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and innovation performance, and the dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation of firms appear to differ in their role and direction on innovation performance, with variability in the degree of positive impact of the innovation dimension and the proactive dimension on innovation performance (Li et al., 2010). Jiang et al. (2010) used market orientation as an intermediary variable in the research on the impact of entrepreneurial orientation on organizational performance, and explored how entrepreneurial orientation has an effect on organizational performance through market orientation. Du and Liu (2014) studied the relationship between market orientation, entrepreneurial orientation and innovation performance from two dimensions of market orientation, reactive and active. The results show that reactive market orientation plays a mediating role in the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on incremental innovation. Proactive market orientation negatively moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and incremental innovation. In the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and breakthrough

innovation, proactive market orientation and reactive market orientation play a mediating role and a negative regulating role, respectively. Liu (2016) dynamically considered market orientation as a mediating variable between business model innovation and manufacturing enterprises' servitization transformation in his study exploring business model innovation on servitization transformation, and examined the direct and indirect effects of (efficiency and novelty) business model innovation on manufacturing enterprises' servitization transformation using proactive market orientation as a mediating variable to again validate the theoretical logic of strategy-behavior-performance. Empirical research shows that (efficiency and novelty) business model innovation has a certain difference in the impact of servitization transformation of manufacturing enterprises.

Moderator variable: institutional environment

The institutional environment, with its embeddedness (Granovetter, 1985), affects the role between corporate strategy and performance. It should be noted that how the institutional elements are brought into the research design will be the first problem faced by the theoretical derivation. Liu (2009) proposed three operational approaches for institution introduction: first, to treat the system as a background, that is, to treat the institution as a moderator variable; it affects the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable; to examine how institutions affect corporate strategy and corporate behavior; second, to treat institutions as causes (Cause & Antecedent, 2009), and explain what strategic behaviors institutional factors induce; third, to study the problem of institutionalization, that is, the process of institutionalization of organizations. To study how the institution changed, how it happened and how the process came into being (Liu, 2009). The above point of view not only points out the method of how to introduce the institution into the theoretical model, but also summarizes the research on the relationship between the institution and strategy in the past two decades.

Table 2 Relevant studies on the moderating effect of institutional environment

Author	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Adjustment variables	Conclusion
Li (2007)	CBO ambidexterity	Company Performance	Institutional Environment	Complex moderating effect
Sheng et al. (2013)	Products, technological breakthroughs	Innovation Performance	Institutional Environment	Complex moderating effect
Shinklo & Mceann (2014)	New Product Development	Corporate Financial Performance	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Wanget et al. (2015)	Corporate Collective	Innovation Performance	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Yang (2018)	Environmental Management	Corporate Performance	Institutional Environment	Complex moderating effect
Wang and Zhao (2013)	Strategic Leadership Behavior	Entrepreneurship	Institutional Environment	Negative moderating effect
Chen and Li (2016)	Market Demand	R&D Location Selection	Institutional Quality	Positive moderating effect
Liu (2017)	Entrepreneurial Orientation	Corporate Performance	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Zhou (2018)	Entrepreneurial Orientation	Business Growth	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect

Wei and Song (2018)	Overall cognitive framework	Innovation Performance	Institutional Environment	Negative moderating effect
Ding (2018)	Independent Director Governance	Financial Risk	Institutional Environment	Complex moderating effect
Li et al. (2018)	Overseas Network Embeddedness	Internationalization Performance	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Zhang and Tian (2018)	Environmental Regulation	Technology Innovation	Institutional Context	Negative moderating effect
Zhou and Wang (2019)	Passion for Entrepreneurship	Failure to learn	Institutional Environment	Negative moderating effect
Ren et al. (2019)	Startup Team Heterogeneity	Innovation Performance	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Ma and Li (2019)	Geographical distance	Technology Transfer	Institutional Background	Negative moderating effect
Li and Yan (2019)	Venture Capital	Innovation Output	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Meng et al. (2019)	Corporate Social Responsibility	Organizational Legitimacy	Institutional Perception	Positive moderating effect
Shai et al. (2019)	Enterprise Knowledge Filtering	Employee Separation	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Liu et al. (2019)	Previous Experience	Corporate decisions M&A	Institutional Environment	Negative moderating effect
Li and Lu (2019)	R&D Internationalization	Corporate Innovation Performance	Institutional Distance	Positive moderating effect
Lu et al. (2019)	Heterogenous performance pressure	External R&D	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Chen et al. (2019)	International Diversity	Innovation Performance	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Li and Luo (2019)	Technology M&A	Innovation Performance	Institutional Environment	Positive moderating effect
Ran and Yang (2020)	International technology spillover	Green Technology Innovation	Institutional Environment	Complex moderating effect
Yang and Zhao (2020)	Open Innovation	Innovation Performance	Institutional Environment	Complex moderating effect

All of the above studies have a common feature, that is, they use the institutional background of emerging economic countries, including China, as a moderator variable. The reason is that the rapid economic growth of emerging economies is the main reason for the internalization of institutions in strategic management and organizational management research (Peng, 1996). In the process of China's transition economy, the institution in the process of changing from planned economy to market economy is exerting an important influence on China's macroeconomic efficiency and micro enterprise performance at the macro and micro levels through various ways. Therefore, in terms of empirical research, scholars have also tried to discover and explore the impact and mechanism of action of institutional change at the micro level, and have used the institutional environment as a moderating factor and established an analytical framework to conduct research. The essence of China's institutional reform is to

promote the process of marketization. The continuous deepening of marketization will definitely affect the strategic choice of enterprises and the innovation of business models. Therefore, this study uses the institutional environment as a moderator variable, and attempts to study the moderating effect between efficient and novelty-centered business model innovation and enterprise performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

1.Literature research

Literature research method mainly refers to a method of studying the literature results of relevant research fields, collecting and analyzing the relevant information of research contents, understanding the latest research results in this field, and thus comprehensively grasping the research problems to be studied. In the research process, this paper collects relevant theoretical evidence on market orientation, institutional environment, business model innovation, incubator operation performance and other aspects by referring to relevant paper or electronic materials. The main research contents of relevant theories and possible future research directions are clarified, and the collected data are sorted out, while different views put forward by various scholars are analyzed and studied, and then the current research directions, research contents, and research progress in strategic positioning, business model innovation, market orientation of incubator operational performance, institutional environment, business model innovation, and impact mechanisms of incubator operational performance in the Chinese incubator industry are discussed in depth. This paper focuses on the impact of incubator business model innovation on operational performance under different market orientations, namely, the moderating effect of institutional environment on business model innovation and operational performance; the mediating effect of market orientation on business model innovation and operation performance, thus constructing the overall research framework and the theoretical model of the influence of incubator business model innovation on operation performance, laying a solid theoretical foundation for the research of this paper, and at the same time giving suggestions and management practice inspiration for incubator operation management. The sources of information in this paper mainly include online and self-media information, among which the online information is mainly from CNKI, and the public information is mainly from the website of the Torch Center of the Ministry of Science and Technology of China.

Questionnaire survey

One of the important research methods in this paper is the questionnaire survey method, based on reading the relevant literature, collecting and organizing the measurement questionnaires of the variables by understanding the relevant literature, adjusting the details to set the questionnaires in line with the actual content of this study, and then distributing and collecting the questionnaires according to the research subjects of the paper, and finally organizing the data collected from the questionnaires. The survey object of this research is the incubator enterprises registered by the Torch Center of the Ministry of Science and Technology of China. The questionnaires are all distributed to employees of incubator companies that have obtained incubator certification, including senior management, operation and service personnel, and grassroots staff of the incubator, in order to gain a relatively comprehensive understanding of the key aspects of the incubator and to demonstrate the impact of business model innovation on the operational performance of the incubator. This study mainly uses the scales used in the existing literature. However, due to the limitations of the industry, there are few relevant references and studies, and some adjustments is made in the existing similar scales in combination with the content of this study. . The questionnaire is based on a five-point Likert

scale. In the process of designing the questionnaire, great reference is made to the content used by the predecessors, especially from existing doctoral dissertations with relevant content, and full communication is made with peers from the research incubator to listen to their valuable opinions. Finally, due to the epidemic situation, the distribution and collection of questionnaires are mainly completed online. The URL of the online questionnaire is directly sent to the relevant incubator staff, who could directly fill in the online questionnaire, and the results are directly saved in the server.

Empirical research method

Using a standardized empirical analysis process, through literature search and analysis, hypotheses are formulated regarding the correlation between variables, samples that meet the requirements are selected, sample data are obtained from the communication with incubator practitioners, in-depth research on the process of incubator utilization and questionnaires are developed for the issues that we want to study. Finally, hypothesis testing is conducted using relevant statistical methods. Through the reliability and validity test, analysis of the relationship between variables, regression analysis and other empirical processing methods, and using SPSS 26.0 software and AOMS23.0 to analyze the data.

Population / Sampling / Unit of Analysis

This study uses a questionnaire survey to obtain the required sample data, and mainly selects incubator enterprises in Guangdong Province, which is the most active region for innovation and entrepreneurship in China, and has the largest number of incubator enterprises and the highest concentration, so it can better reflect the relationship between business model innovation and operational performance of incubator enterprises under different strategic positions in the context of the high development of innovation and entrepreneurship in China. Sample selection adopted the method of sampling survey. Sampling survey means to select only a part of the research objects, conduct investigation on this part of the objects, and then deduce and summarize the overall characteristics of the samples according to the sampling results. The method of sampling survey has the advantages of strong operability, simple operation, low cost, short time, less objective constraints and abundant information. In view of the sampling survey adopted, in order to make the results more comprehensive and data more reliable, subjective sampling was adopted to issue questionnaires to the incubators in Guangdong Province in cooperation with China Guangdong Incubator Industry Association to ensure that the respondents are practitioners of the industry. The distribution of this questionnaire survey was conducted online, and a total of 402 original data samples were obtained. Excluding invalid questionnaires that were incomplete or had obvious errors, there were 385 valid questionnaires, and the effective completion rate of questionnaires was 95.77%. The survey respondents came from state-owned and private incubator enterprises and incubator enterprises of universities and research institutions, national, provincial and local municipal incubator enterprises as well as incubator in the process of qualification declaration, with operation time ranging from 1 year to more than 10 years.

Profile of Respondents

In this paper, a total of 385 valid samples are collected and analyzed in terms of incubator sponsor background, whether or not they are incubator operation managers, incubator operation time, and incubator level, as described in Table 3: The respondents of this questionnaire survey are operation and management personnel at all levels in the incubator industry. The sample companies cover incubators from the government, state-owned, private enterprises, universities and other backgrounds.

Table 3 Description analysis of basic information

Nature	Category	Number of people	Percentage/%
	1	77	20
Sponsor background of your incubator	2	216	56.1
	3	39	10.1
	4	53	13.8
Whether to be an incubator operation manager	1	250	64.9
	2	135	35.1
Your incubator operating hours	1	70	18.2
	2	151	39.2
	3	89	23.1
	4	66	17.1
	5	9	2.3
The qualification level of your incubator	1	42	10.9
	2	158	41
	3	68	17.7
	4	117	30.4

The operating time ranges from 1 year to more than 10 years, the qualification level covers the national, provincial, prefecture-level and incubators under application. The above are all reference elements for the research of incubator enterprises.

Sample Reliability Analysis

There are 8 factors in this study, namely efficiency-centered business model innovation, novelty-centered business model innovation, reactive market orientation, proactive market orientation, institutional environment, incubation efficiency, economic efficiency, brand and social efficiency. The reliability of each variable is analyzed one by one as follows, and the measurement results are shown in Table 4:

Table 4 Reliability Analysis 1

Dimension	Item	CITC	Cronbach's Alpha if item deleted	Cronbach's
Efficiency-centered business model innovation	A1	0.614	0.875	0.884
	A2	0.777	0.853	
	A3	0.698	0.864	
	A4	0.659	0.869	
	A5	0.666	0.869	
	A6	0.673	0.868	
	A7	0.631	0.873	
	A8	0.794	0.906	
	A9	0.692	0.914	
	A10	0.662	0.915	
Novelty-centered business model innovation	A11	0.65	0.916	0.921
	A12	0.72	0.912	
	A13	0.786	0.907	
	A14	0.799	0.906	
	A15	0.698	0.913	
	A16	0.659	0.916	
Reactive market orientation	B1	0.676	0.803	0.843
	B2	0.569	0.832	
	B3	0.631	0.815	
	B4	0.637	0.813	
Proactive market orientation	B5	0.73	0.788	0.871
	B6	0.713	0.84	
	B7	0.7	0.844	
	B8	0.666	0.852	

	B9	0.646	0.856	
	B10	0.764	0.827	
	C1	0.734	0.918	
	C2	0.681	0.921	
	C3	0.629	0.924	
	C4	0.717	0.919	
Institutional Environment	C5	0.639	0.922	0.927
	C6	0.698	0.92	
	C7	0.781	0.916	
	C8	0.671	0.921	
	C9	0.732	0.919	
	C10	0.758	0.917	
	C11	0.689	0.92	
Incubation efficiency	D1	0.691	0.674	0.799
	D2	0.581	0.791	
	D3	0.663	0.707	
Economic efficiency	D4	0.718	0.721	0.825
	D5	0.641	0.798	
	D6	0.684	0.755	
Brand and social efficiency	D7	0.717	0.809	0.855
	D8	0.738	0.799	
	D9	0.746	0.783	

It can be seen from the above table that the Cronbach's alpha coefficients of efficiency-centered business model innovation, novelty-centered business model innovation, reactive market orientation, proactive market orientation, institutional environment, incubation efficiency, economic efficiency, brand and social efficiency are all greater than the standard of 0.7 , indicating that the variables have good internal consistency reliability. CITC are all greater than the standard of 0.5, indicating that the measurement items meet the research requirements. From value of "Cronbach's alpha if item deleted", deleting any item will not cause the increase of Cronbach's alpha value, which also indicates that the variable has good reliability.

Exploratory factor analysis

Factor analysis of business model innovation

Exploratory factor analysis is conducted using SPSS 23.0, and KMO and Bartlett's test are performed on the scales, results are shown in Table 5 :

Table 5 KMO and Bartlett's Test 1

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.936
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3390.433
	df	120
	Sig.	.000

It can be obtained from the above table that KMO=0.936, which is greater than 0.7, and the Bartlett's test of sphericity value is significant (Sig.<0.001), indicating that the questionnaire data meets the premise requirements of factor analysis. Therefore, for further analysis, the principal component analysis method is used for factor extraction, and the common factor is extracted with an eigenvalue greater than 1 as the factor, when factor rotation varimax orthogonal rotation is used for factor analysis. The analysis results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Factor analysis results 1

Item	Components					
	Novelty-centered innovation	business	model	Efficiency-centered innovation	business	model
A8	0.853			0.086		
A14	0.825			0.211		
A13	0.808			0.229		
A9	0.76			0.099		
A12	0.76			0.199		
A16	0.75			0.025		
A15	0.718			0.287		
A11	0.7			0.172		
A10	0.699			0.217		
A2	0.227			0.819		
A6	0.055			0.779		
A3	0.158			0.773		
A4	0.162			0.735		
A5	0.237			0.725		
A7	0.153			0.715		
A1	0.129			0.707		
Eigenvalue	5.473			4.265		
% of Variance variance	34.208			26.655		
Cumulative % of Variance	34.208			60.862		

It can be seen from the above table that a total of two factors are obtained from the factor analysis results, and the overall explanatory power reached 60.862% and is greater than 50%, indicating that the two screened factors are well representative. The Factor loading coefficient is shown in the table above. The factor loading of each measurement item is greater than 0.5, and the cross loading is less than 0.4. Each item falls into the corresponding factor, indicating that the scale has good construct validity.

Factor analysis of Market orientation

Exploratory factor analysis is conducted using SPSS 23.0, and KMO and Bartlett's test are performed on the scales, results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 KMO and Bartlett's Test 2

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy	0.877
Approx. Chi-Square	1651.678
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df
	45
	Sig.
	.000

It can be obtained from the above table that KMO=0.877, which is greater than 0.7, and the Bartlett's test of sphericity value is significant (Sig.<0.001), indicating that the questionnaire data meets the premise requirements of factor analysis. Therefore, for further analysis, the

principal component analysis method is used for factor extraction, and the common factor is extracted with an eigenvalue greater than 1 as the factor, when factor rotation varimax orthogonal rotation is used for factor analysis. The analysis results are shown in Table 8:

Table 8 Factor analysis results 2

Item	Components	
	Proactive market orientation	Reactive market orientation
B10	0.85	0.139
B6	0.818	0.115
B7	0.803	0.129
B8	0.783	0.103
B9	0.759	0.127
B5	0.14	0.833
B1	0.146	0.792
B4	0.153	0.759
B3	0.179	0.748
B2	-0.001	0.737
Eigenvalue	3.321	3.076
% of Variance	33.215	30.758
Cumulative % of Variance	33.215	63.973

It can be seen from the above table that a total of two factors are obtained from the factor analysis results, and the overall explanatory power reached 63.973% and is greater than 50%, indicating that the two screened factors are well representative. The Factor loading coefficient is shown in the table above. The factor loading of each measurement item is greater than 0.5, and the cross loading is less than 0.4. Each item falls into the corresponding factor, indicating that the scale has good construct validity.

Factor analysis of institutional environmental

Exploratory factor analysis is conducted using SPSS 23.0, and KMO and Bartlett's test are performed on the scales, results are shown in Table 9.

Table 9 KMO and Bartlett's Test 3

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.951
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2393.15
	df	55
	Sig.	.000

It can be seen from the above table that KMO=0.951, which is greater than 0.7, and the Bartlett's test of sphericity value is significant (Sig.<0.001), indicating that the questionnaire data meets the premise requirements of factor analysis. Therefore, for further analysis, the principal component analysis method is used for factor extraction, and the common factor is extracted with an eigenvalue greater than 1 as the factor, when factor rotation varimax orthogonal rotation is used for factor analysis. The analysis results are shown in Table 10. It can be seen from the above table that a total of one factors are obtained from the factor analysis results, and the overall explanatory power reached 57.99% and is greater than 50%, indicating that the one screened factors are well representative.

Table 10 Factor analysis results 3

Item	Components
	Institutional Environment
C7	0.828
C10	0.81
C1	0.788
C9	0.788
C4	0.774
C6	0.758
C11	0.747
C2	0.744
C8	0.733
C5	0.703
C3	0.692
Eigenvalue	6.379
% of Variance	57.99
Cumulative % of Variance	57.99

The Factor loading coefficient is shown in the table above. The factor loading of each measurement item is greater than 0.5, and each item falls into the corresponding factor, indicating that the scale has good construct validity.

Factor analysis of incubator operational performance

Exploratory factor analysis is conducted using SPSS 23.0, and KMO and Bartlett's test are performed on the scales, results are shown in Table 11.

Table 11 KMO and Bartlett's Test 4

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy adequacy		0.869
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1635.99
	df	36
	Sig.	.000

It can be obtained from the above table that KMO=0.869, which is greater than 0.7, and the Bartlett's test of sphericity value is significant (Sig.<0.001), indicating that the questionnaire data meets the premise requirements of factor analysis. Therefore, for further analysis, the principal component analysis method is used for factor extraction, and the common factor is extracted with an eigenvalue greater than 1 as the factor, when factor rotation varimax orthogonal rotation is used for factor analysis. The analysis results are shown in Table 12.

It can be seen from the above table that a total of three factors are obtained from the factor analysis results, and the overall explanatory power reached 74.978% and is greater than 50%, indicating that the three screened factors are well representative. The Factor loading coefficient is shown in the table above. The factor loading of each measurement item is greater than 0.5, and each item falls into the corresponding factor, indicating that the scale has good construct validity.

Table 12 Factor analysis results 4

Item	Components			
	Brand and Efficiency	Social	Economic Efficiency	Incubation Efficiency
D7	0.856		0.18	0.157
D8	0.816		0.265	0.197
D9	0.793		0.262	0.295
D5	0.132		0.843	0.139
D4	0.286		0.811	0.173
D6	0.287		0.761	0.253
D1	0.216		0.243	0.803
D3	0.268		0.135	0.801
D2	0.112		0.152	0.799
Eigenvalue	2.339		2.22	2.188
% of Variance	25.994		24.669	24.315
Cumulative % of Variance	25.994		50.663	74.978

Confirmatory factor analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis of business model innovation

There are two dimensions, namely, efficiency-centered business model innovation and novelty-centered business model innovation, which include a total of 16 measurement items. After performing confirmatory factor analysis, the following Figure 1 and Table 13 are obtained.

Figure 1 Confirmatory factor analysis of business model innovation

Table 13 Goodness of fit of confirmatory factor model 1

Goodness of fit Indicators of model	Reference standard value	Statistical values	Goodness of fit
CMIN	--	200.91	--
DF	--	103	--
CMIN/DF	<3	1.951	Good
RMR	<0.08	0.046	Good
GFI	>0.8	0.941	Good
AGFI	>0.8	0.922	Good
NFI	>0.9	0.942	Good
IFI	>0.9	0.971	Good
TLI	>0.9	0.966	Good
CFI	>0.9	0.971	Good
RMSEA	<0.08	0.05	Good

From the above table, it can be seen that CMIN/DF is 1.951, which is less than the standard of 3. GFI, AGFI, NFI, IFI, TLI, and CFI all reach the standard of 0.9 or more, RMR is 0.046, which is less than 0.08, RMSEA is 0.05 and less than 0.08. All the goodness-of-fit indicators meet the general research standard, so it can be considered that this model has a nice goodness of fit.

Table 14 Confirmatory factor analysis results 1

Variables	Item	Factor loading	CR	AVE
Efficiency-centered Business Innovation Model	A1	0.659	0.885	0.525
	A2	0.842		
	A3	0.752		
	A4	0.71		
	A5	0.72		
	A6	0.702		
	A7	0.67		
	A8	0.824		
	A9	0.719		
	A10	0.691		
Novelty-centered Business Innovation Model	A11	0.682	0.922	0.568
	A12	0.757		
	A13	0.825		
	A14	0.845		
	A15	0.734		
	A16	0.683		

From Table 14, it can be seen that the standardized factor loadings of each measurement index of efficiency-centered business model innovation and novelty-centered business model innovation is greater than 0.6, the composite reliability (CR) is greater than 0.7, and the average

variation extracted (AVE) is greater than 0.5, indicating that each variable has good convergent validity.

Confirmatory factor analysis of market orientation

There are two dimensions, namely reactive market orientation and proactive market orientation, which include a total of 10 measurement items. After performing confirmatory factor analysis, the following Figure 2 and Table 15 are obtained.

Figure 2 Confirmatory factor analysis of market orientation

Table 15 Goodness of fit of confirmatory factor model 2

Goodness of fit Indicators of model	Reference standard value	Statistical values	Goodness of fit
CMIN	--	39.836	--
DF	--	34	--
CMIN/DF	<3	1.172	Good
RMR	<0.08	0.032	Good
GFI	>0.8	0.98	Good
AGFI	>0.8	0.967	Good
NFI	>0.9	0.976	Good
IFI	>0.9	0.996	Good
TLI	>0.9	0.995	Good
CFI	>0.9	0.996	Good
RMSEA	<0.08	0.021	Good

From the above table, it can be seen that CMIN/DF is 1.172, which is less than the standard of 3. GFI, AGFI, NFI, IFI, TLI, and CFI all reach the standard of 0.9 or more, RMR is 0.032, which is less than 0.08, RMSEA is 0.021 and less than 0.08. All the goodness-of-fit indicators meet the general research standard, so it can be considered that this model has a nice goodness of fit.

Table 16 Confirmatory factor analysis results 2

Variables	Item	Factor loading	CR	AVE
Reactive Orientation	Market B1	0.749	0.845	0.523
	B2	0.628		
	B3	0.707		
	B4	0.71		
	B5	0.809		
	B6	0.775		
Proactive Orientation	Market B7	0.757	0.872	0.578
	B8	0.724		
	B9	0.701		
	B10	0.837		

It can be seen from the above table that the standardized factor loading of each measurement index of reactive market orientation and proactive market orientation is greater than 0.6, the composite reliability (CR) is greater than 0.7, and the average variation extracted (AVE) is greater than 0.5, indicating that each variable has good convergent validity.

Confirmatory factor analysis of institutional environment

There is a total of 1 dimension including 11 measurement items. After performing confirmatory factor analysis, the following Figure 3 and Table 17 are obtained.

Figure 3 Confirmatory factor analysis of institutional environment

Table 17 Goodness of fit of confirmatory factor model 3

Goodness of fit indicators of model	Reference standard value	Statistical values	Goodness of fit
CMIN	--	128.335	--
DF	--	44	--
CMIN/DF	<3	2.917	Good
RMR	<0.08	0.035	Good
GFI	>0.8	0.94	Good
AGFI	>0.8	0.91	Good
NFI	>0.9	0.947	Good
IFI	>0.9	0.965	Good
TLI	>0.9	0.955	Good
CFI	>0.9	0.964	Good
RMSEA	<0.08	0.071	Good

From the above table, it can be seen that CMIN/DF is 2.917, which is less than the standard of 3. GFI, AGFI, NFI, IFI, TLI, and CFI all reach the standard of 0.9 or more, RMR is 0.035, which is less than 0.08, RMSEA is 0.05 and less than 0.08. All the goodness-of-fit indicators meet the general research standard, so it can be considered that this model has a nice goodness of fit.

Table 18 Confirmatory factor analysis results 3

Variables	Item	Factor loading	CR	AVE
Institutional Environment	C1	0.766	0.928	0.539
	C2	0.708		
	C3	0.657		
	C4	0.747		
	C5	0.665		
	C6	0.734		
	C7	0.815		
	C8	0.697		
	C9	0.763		
	C10	0.791		
	C11	0.715		

From Table 4-18, it can be seen that the standardized factor loading of each measurement index of the institutional environment is greater than 0.6, the composite reliability (CR) is greater than 0.7, and the average variation extracted (AVE) is greater than 0.5, indicating that each variable has good convergent validity.

Confirmatory factor analysis of incubator operational performance

There are 3 dimensions, namely incubation efficiency, economic efficiency, brand and social efficiency, which include a total of 9 measurement items. After performing confirmatory factor analysis, the following Figure 4 and Table 19 are obtained.

Figure 4 Confirmatory factor analysis of operational performance

Table 19 Goodness of fit of confirmatory factor model 4

Goodness of fit indicators of model	Reference standard value	Statistical values	Goodness of fit
CMIN	--	27.007	--
DF	--	24	--
CMIN/DF	<3	1.125	Good
RMR	<0.08	0.019	Good
GFI	>0.8	0.984	Good
AGFI	>0.8	0.971	Good
NFI	>0.9	0.984	Good
IFI	>0.9	0.998	Good
TLI	>0.9	0.997	Good
CFI	>0.9	0.998	Good
RMSEA	<0.08	0.018	Good

From the above table, it can be seen that CMIN/DF is 1.125, which is less than the standard of 3. GFI, AGFI, NFI, IFI, TLI, and CFI all reach the standard of 0.9 or more, RMR is 0.019, which is less than 0.08, and RMSEA is 0.018 and less than 0.08. All the goodness-of-fit indicators meet the general research standard, so it can be considered that this model has a nice goodness of fit.

Table 20 Confirmatory factor analysis results 4

Variables	Item	Factor loading	CR	AVE
Operational Performance	Incubation efficiency	0.728	0.832	0.624
	Economic efficiency	0.791		
	Brand and Social Efficiency	0.847		
Incubation efficiency	D1	0.834	0.804	0.58
	D2	0.652		
	D3	0.786		
	D4	0.83		
Economic efficiency	D5	0.706	0.826	0.614
	D6	0.81		
	D7	0.779		
Brand and Social Efficiency	D8	0.819	0.859	0.67
	D9	0.856		

It can be seen from the above table that the standardized factor loading of each measurement index of operational performance, incubation efficiency, economic efficiency, brand and social efficiency is greater than 0.6, the composite reliability (CR) is greater than 0.7, and the average variation extracted (AVE) is greater than 0.5, indicating that each variable has good convergent validity.

Discriminant validity

In this study, the more rigorous AVE method is used to evaluate the discriminant validity. (Fornell and Larcker,1981), The square root value of the AVE of each factor must be greater than the correlation coefficient of each paired variable, indicating that the factors have discriminant validity. The square root value of AVE of each factor is greater than the standardized correlation coefficient outside the diagonal line, so this study still has discriminant validity, and the lower oblique triangle is the correlation coefficient. See Table 21 below for more details

Table 21 Discriminant Validity

	Efficiency-centered Business Model Innovation	Novelty-centered Business Model Innovation	Reactive Market Orientation	Proactive Market Orientation	Institutional Environment	Operational Performance
Efficiency-centered Business Model Innovation	0.725					
Novelty-centered Business Model Innovation	.417**	0.754				
Reactive Market Orientation	.483**	.402**	0.723			
Proactive Market Orientation	.308**	.425**	.304**	0.760		

Institutional Environment	.283**	.335**	.257**	.316**	0.734
Operational Performance	.504**	.528**	.618**	.534**	0.790

Note: **, P<0.01, The bold value in black is the square root value of AVE

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Before empirical test, an initial structural equations model should be constructed. The initial models constructed in this study can be divided into structural models and measurement models. The core task is to build a structural model and determine all latent variables involved in the initial model. Before constructing the initial model, the relationship and role of each variable must be determined. Of course, this relationship and role need to be further verified to be known. This paper sets up five latent variables: efficiency-centered business model innovation, novelty-centered business model innovation, reactive market orientation, proactive market orientation, and operational performance. Studying the relationships and roles among the latent variables is the key to constructing the initial model and is a necessary step in constructing the structural model. After constructing the structural model, the measurement model needs to be established, that is, the relationship between each latent variable and the observed variable (question item) to which it belongs needs to be determined in advance. In this paper, the conceptual model is combined with several research hypotheses and relevant considerations in the initial model construction to first construct the initial model shown in Figure 5, which lay the foundation for further empirical validation.

Figure 5 Initial SEM model diagram

Model analysis and goodness of fit test

The calculation is performed using AMOS23.0, the maximum likelihood method is used for estimation, and the results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 SEM model diagram

From the following table, it can be seen that CMIN/DF is 1.381, which is less than the standard below 3, AGFI statistic is 0.887, which is greater than 0.8 and within the acceptable range, GFI, NFI, IFI, TLI, and CFI all reach the standard above 0.9, RMR is 0.042, which is less than 0.08, RMSEA is 0.031 which is less than 0.08, and each goodness-of-fit index meets the general research criteria, so it can be considered that this model has a nice goodness of fit, as in Table 4-22.

Table 22 Test results of goodness of fit of model

Goodness of fit indicators of model	Reference standard value	Statistical values	Goodness of fit
CMIN	--	756.655	--
DF	--	548	--
CMIN/DF	<3	1.381	Good
RMR	<0.08	0.042	Good
GFI	>0.8	0.902	Good
AGFI	>0.8	0.887	Acceptable
NFI	>0.9	0.902	Good
IFI	>0.9	0.971	Good
TLI	>0.9	0.968	Good
CFI	>0.9	0.971	Good
RMSEA	<0.08	0.031	Good

Mediation effect test

In this study, the method of Bootstrapping is used to verify the mediation effect. Studies have shown that if the bootstrap confidence interval does not contain 0, the corresponding indirect, direct or total effect exists. The Bias-Corrected 95% confidence intervals are obtained by running the Bootstrap method 5000 times in AMOS 23.0, as shown in Table 23 . It can be seen from the above table that in the total effect, the total effect value of efficiency-centered business model innovation on operational performance is 0.4, and neither the Bias-Corrected nor the Percentile 95% CI contained 0 within the interval of values of lower and upper, indicating that the total effect exist; the total effect value of novelty-centered business model innovation on operational performance is 0.45, and and neither the Bias-Corrected nor the Percentile 95% CI contained 0 within the interval of values of lower and upper, indicating that the total effect exists.

Table 23 Mediation effect test

	Standardized coefficient	Bias-Corrected		Percentile	
		95% CI		95% CI	
		Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
Total effect					
Efficiency-centered Business Model Innovation on operational performance	0.4	0.31	0.486	0.309	0.485
Novelty-centered Business Model Innovation innovation on operational performance	0.45	0.334	0.553	0.334	0.552
Indirect effect					
Efficiency-centered Business Model Innovation - Reactive Market Orientation - Operational Performance	0.21	0.138	0.328	0.133	0.317
Novelty-centered Business Model Innovation innovation - Reactive market orientation - Operational performance	0.128	0.073	0.227	0.068	0.213
Efficiency-centered Business Model Innovation - Proactive Market Orientation - Operational Performance	0.065	0.023	0.125	0.021	0.12
Novel Business Model Innovation - Proactive Market Orientation - Operational Performance	0.146	0.089	0.224	0.086	0.219
Direct effect					
Efficiency-centered Business Model Innovation on operational performance	0.125	0.013	0.222	0.015	0.225
Novelty-centered Business Model Innovation on operational performance	0.175	0.06	0.27	0.062	0.272

In the indirect effect, the indirect effect of efficiency-centered business model innovation on operational performance through reactive market orientation is 0.21, and neither the Bias-Corrected nor the Percentile 95% CI contained 0 within the interval of values of lower and upper, indicating that the indirect effect exist; the indirect effect value of novelty-centered business model innovation on operational performance through reactive market orientation is 0.128, and neither the Bias-Corrected nor the Percentile 95% CI contained 0 within the interval of values of lower and upper, indicating that the indirect effect exists. The indirect effect value of efficiency-centered business model innovation on operational performance through proactive market orientation is 0.065, and neither the Bias-Corrected nor the Percentile 95% CI contained 0 within the interval of values of lower and upper, indicating the existence of indirect effects; The indirect effect value of novelty-centered business model innovation on operational performance through proactive market orientation is 0.146, and neither the Bias-Corrected nor the Percentile 95% CI contained 0 within the interval of values of lower and upper, indicating the existence of indirect effects. In the direct effect, the direct effect value of efficiency-centered business model innovation on operational performance is 0.125, and neither the Bias-Corrected nor the Percentile 95% CI contained 0 within the interval of values of lower and upper, indicating that the direct effect exists; novelty-centered business model The direct effect value of model innovation on operational performance is 0.175, and neither the Bias-Corrected nor the Percentile 95% CI contained 0 within the interval of values of lower and upper, indicating that the direct effect exists.

Moderating effect test

Testing the moderating effect of institutional environment in the effect of efficiency-centered business model innovation on operational performance

Taking the efficiency-centered business model innovation as the independent variable, the institutional environment as the moderator variable, and the operational performance as the dependent variable, the moderating effect test analysis is carried out. As shown in Table 24.

Table 24 Moderating effect test 1

	Operational Performance		
	M1	M2	M3
	β	β	β
Efficiency-centered business model innovation	0.504***	0.406***	0.405***
Institutional Environment		0.345***	0.33***
Institutional Environment x Efficiency-centered business model innovation			0.115**
R2	0.254	0.363	0.376
Δ R2	0.254	0.109	0.013
F	130.438***	109.026***	76.667***

Note: *, p<0.05; **, p<0.01; ***, p<0.001

It can be simulated from the model in the table above that the institutional environment x efficiency-centered business model innovation has a significant positive impact on operational performance ($\beta=0.115$, $p<0.05$), indicating that institutional environment has a significant positive moderating effect on the relationship between operational performance and efficiency-centered business model innovation, and the hypothesis is valid. As shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Moderating Effect Test Diagram 1

Testing the moderating effect of institutional environment in the impact of novelty-centered business model innovation on operational performance

Taking the novelty-centered business model innovation as the independent variable, the institutional environment as the moderator variable, and the operational performance as the dependent variable, the moderating effect test analysis is carried out.

Table 25 Moderating effect test 2

		Operational Performance		
		M1	M2	M3
		β	β	β
Novelty-centered Business Model Innovation		0.528***	0.421***	0.429***
Institutional Environment			0.319***	0.291***
Institutional Environment x Novelty-centered Business Model Innovation				0.1*
R2		0.279	0.369	0.378
$\Delta R2$		0.279	0.09	0.009
F		147.882***	111.573***	77.221***

Note: *, p<0.05; **, p<0.01; ***, p<0.001

It can be simulated from the model in the table above that the institutional environment x novelty-centered business model innovation has a significant positive impact on operational performance ($\beta=0.115$, p<0.05), indicating that institutional environment has a significant positive moderating effect on the relationship between operational performance and novelty-centered business model innovation, and the hypothesis is valid.

Figure 8 Moderating Effect Test Diagram 2

Conclusion

The rise and development of the concept of business model innovation is inseparable from the progress of society. Drivers include emerging knowledge, economic development, outsourcing of many business activities, and restructuring of the global financial services industry. Especially in the present situation that incubators need to undertake the task of making money independently, the way of making money is different from that of industrial enterprises. In

industrial companies, where scale is important, the problem of capturing value is relatively simple: companies simply sell their technology and intellectual property or products. As a subdivision type of service enterprise, how to reflect the value of service has become an important topic of business model innovation. This study analyzes the impact of business model innovation on the operational performance of incubator companies, the mediating role of market orientation, and the regulatory role played by the institutional environment. Incubator companies need to constantly seek new ways to grow, putting them in the reality of business and telling managers how tough the competition is. The shortage of hardware conditions can be compensated by the innovation of business models to a certain extent. Software and flexible services are the core of incubator enterprises, which also puts forward higher requirements for the design and innovation of business models. The business model innovation of incubator enterprises can become a kind of pilot, which can be widely used in service-oriented enterprises to make up for the general congenital deficiencies of domestic tertiary industry enterprises. Business model innovation clarifies the logic, data, and other evidence that supports the customer value proposition, as well as the feasible structure of business revenues and costs to achieve that value. In short, business model innovation reflects the value a company brings to customers, how it provides value, and how it derives its own benefits from value. A good business model innovation will provide considerable value to customers and capture a portion of the revenue. But developing a successful business model innovation, no matter how novel, is not enough by itself to guarantee a competitive advantage. All in all, the basic elements of business model innovation are usually fairly transparent and in principle easy to imitate, in fact, imitation is usually only a matter of a few years. In practice, successful business model innovations often become, to some extent, the "shared" work of multiple competitors. The issues associated with good business model innovation are all interrelated and at the heart of the fundamental questions that business strategists ask—how to build sustainable competitive advantage, and how to achieve excess profits? Simply put, business model innovation defines how a business creates and delivers value to customers and then converts the payments received into profits. From the perspective of innovation profit, business pioneers must be good at not only product innovation, but also business model innovation, understanding business model innovation options, customer needs, and technology trajectories. Developing a successful business model innovation is not enough to ensure the sustainability of competitiveness, so an effective business model innovation that is differentiated and difficult to imitate is more likely to generate profits. If the business model innovation is sufficiently differentiated and difficult to replicate, then the business model innovation itself can be a way to gain competitive advantage and bring great significance to the local business incubation and industrial restructuring.

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